

Gotta Catch 'Em All! Sequence Flaws in CEGAR for Classical Planning (Supplementary Material)

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1 Extended Experiments Results

This section shows full coverage tables and additional tables and plots not included in the main paper.

1.1 Single Abstraction

Plots of Figure 1 show the total time of the heuristics whose expansions are compared in the main paper, as a complement of those plots. In the first three plots we can see that tasks solved in less than 100 seconds are penalized for F_{it} , due to the higher time to build the abstraction, especially in a comparison against F , which only finds a flaw at each step. In the last plot it is clear that the high time needed to build abstractions of B_{CGr} is the biggest handicap against B .

Table 1 shows the coverage of each technique at each domain, so the performance in each domain can be compared. This table was not included in the main paper due to its size. We can observe in this table the divergences in coverage among domains, especially for CGr , which is the best at some domains but bad at the rest. This makes it a good strategy to complement the best ones and it also suggests that different variable orders could also be effective in different domains. CGr is effective in *blocksworld*, *data-network*, *depots*, *logistics*, *parking*, *pipesworld*, *scanalyzer*, *snake*, *storage*, *tetris* and *tidybot*, which suggests that refining the goals and the variables causally related to goals is important in these domains.

1.2 Additive Abstractions

The statistics table for additive abstractions was not included in the main paper due to space limitations, but it is shown in 2. They are lower but with a similar trend than the statistics for a single abstraction, as is described in the main paper. It is specially interesting the fact that flaws are found much closer to the initial state than for a single abstraction, which happens because the tasks are smaller (with a single goal), so a lower number of flaws exists in each abstraction.

The last table is the coverage at each domain (Table 3). This table also shows that CGr is the best at some domains but bad in the rest, although the domains slightly change, and it is bad at *data-network* and *depots* domains and good at *pegsol*. Also, the differences among domains are reduced because the relevance of refinements is reduced by the positive effects of cost partitioning.

Figure 1: Total time of selected single-abstraction strategies.

Table 1: Coverage of different strategies building a single abstraction. A bold value means the maximum value and * variant is the best strategy at each direction.

Domain	Forward Sequence Flaws								Backward Sequence Flaws								Bidirectional Sequence Flaws									
	F_*	F_{last}	F_{ref}	F_{cost}	F_{CG}	F_{CGr}	F_{it}	B_*	B_{last}	B_{ref}	B_{cost}	B_{CG}	B_{CGr}	B_{it}	D_*	D_{last}	D_{ref}	D_{cost}	D_{CG}	D_{CGr}	D_{it}	D_{clo}				
agricola	6	5	5	5	5	5	6	6	8	8	5	8	8	5	6	8	8	8	5	8	7	3	6	8	8	
airport	6	6	2	2	3	4	2	0	7	7	4	2	2	5	2	6	6	6	5	2	2	5	2	0	3	
barman	13	12	12	12	12	12	10	13	12	12	12	12	12	12	12	12	12	12	12	12	12	12	12	12	12	
blocksworld	13	12	12	12	12	12	13	13	14	13	12	13	13	12	14	12	14	13	12	13	12	12	14	13	13	
childsnack	5	5	5	5	5	5	5	5	5	5	5	5	5	5	5	5	5	5	5	5	5	5	5	5	5	
data-network	12	11	11	11	11	11	12	12	12	12	10	12	12	11	12	12	12	12	10	12	11	11	12	12	12	
depots	13	11	11	11	11	11	11	13	12	11	11	11	11	11	12	12	12	11	11	11	11	12	11	11		
driverlog	8	8	5	8	7	7	6	8	8	8	5	8	8	8	6	8	8	8	5	8	8	7	6	7	5	
elevators	11	11	11	11	11	11	11	11	14	12	11	13	11	11	11	14	13	13	11	12	11	12	11	11	11	
floortile	6	5	5	5	5	6	5	6	7	6	5	6	6	5	6	7	6	6	5	6	6	5	6	6	6	
freecell	6	6	6	6	6	6	6	6	6	6	6	6	6	6	6	6	6	6	6	6	6	6	6	6	6	
ged	24	22	22	22	22	22	16	24	24	24	22	24	23	22	16	22	24	24	22	24	24	22	16	24	24	
grid	19	15	16	16	15	13	11	19	19	19	14	18	18	14	17	17	20	20	14	17	20	13	14	17	16	
gripper	12	12	12	12	12	12	12	12	12	12	12	12	12	12	12	12	12	12	12	12	12	12	12	12	12	
hiking	13	10	12	10	10	10	11	13	13	11	11	11	11	10	13	11	12	11	11	11	12	10	12	11	11	
logistics	13	12	12	12	11	11	13	12	12	12	11	12	12	11	12	12	13	12	11	13	12	11	12	12	12	
miconic	4	4	4	4	4	4	4	4	4	4	4	4	4	4	4	4	4	4	4	4	4	4	4	4	4	
mprime	7	6	7	6	6	5	6	7	8	6	6	6	6	6	5	8	6	7	6	6	6	6	5	7	6	6
nomystery	7	7	6	7	7	7	6	7	7	7	5	7	7	7	5	7	7	7	5	7	7	7	6	6	6	
openstacks	6	6	6	6	6	6	6	6	6	6	6	6	6	6	6	6	6	6	6	6	6	6	6	6	6	
organic-synth	11	11	11	11	11	11	11	10	11	11	11	10	10	10	11	11	11	11	11	11	10	10	9	11	11	11
parcprinter	11	10	8	10	9	11	9	9	12	11	8	11	10	11	12	11	12	11	8	11	11	11	12	8	8	
parking	9	8	8	8	8	8	9	9	9	9	8	9	9	8	9	9	9	9	8	9	9	8	9	9	9	
pathways	10	9	9	9	9	9	10	10	14	9	9	9	9	9	14	9	14	9	9	9	9	14	9	9	9	
pegsol	29	28	29	29	29	29	28	29	29	29	28	29	29	29	29	29	29	29	28	29	28	29	29	29	29	
pipesworld-not	20	18	20	18	18	18	18	20	24	19	18	19	19	17	24	19	20	19	18	19	18	17	20	19	18	
pipesworld-tank	15	14	14	14	14	14	15	14	16	15	15	15	15	14	16	15	16	15	15	15	15	13	16	15	14	
rovers	4	4	4	4	4	4	4	4	4	4	4	4	4	4	4	4	4	4	4	4	4	4	4	4	4	
satellite	5	5	5	5	5	5	5	5	5	5	5	5	5	5	5	5	5	5	5	5	5	5	5	5	5	
scanalyzer	10	9	9	9	9	9	10	9	9	9	9	9	9	9	9	9	10	9	9	9	9	9	10	9	9	
snake	19	15	18	15	15	15	19	18	20	20	15	9	17	14	19	17	19	19	15	5	5	15	19	19	18	
sokoban	10	10	10	9	10	9	8	9	13	11	10	8	7	9	7	13	12	12	10	3	1	9	4	9	10	
storage	6	5	6	5	5	5	6	6	7	6	5	6	6	5	7	6	7	6	5	6	6	5	7	6	6	
termes	19	13	19	13	13	13	16	19	19	19	13	19	19	17	18	15	19	19	13	19	18	16	17	16	19	
tetris	18	18	18	18	18	18	18	18	18	18	18	18	18	17	16	18	18	18	18	18	18	16	15	18	18	
thoughtful	5	5	5	5	5	5	5	5	5	5	5	5	5	5	5	5	5	5	5	5	5	5	5	5	5	
tidybot	10	10	9	10	9	9	10	10	11	10	9	10	10	8	11	10	11	10	9	10	9	9	11	10	10	
tpp	3	3	3	3	3	2	2	3	3	3	2	3	3	2	2	3	3	3	2	3	3	2	2	3	2	
transport	14	12	13	12	12	14	11	13	14	13	12	13	13	14	11	14	14	13	12	13	13	14	11	13	13	
visitall	9	9	8	9	9	9	9	8	10	10	7	10	9	9	9	10	10	10	7	10	9	9	9	8	8	
woodworking	5	5	5	5	5	5	5	5	5	5	5	5	5	5	5	5	5	5	5	5	5	5	5	5	5	
zenotravel	10	9	8	9	9	9	8	10	10	9	7	10	9	9	10	9	10	9	7	10	9	9	9	9	8	
Total	456	416	421	413	410	411	405	437	478	451	400	432	433	412	438	445	470	452	401	422	413	407	425	428	427	

Table 2: Statistics for additive abstractions.

Domain	Forward Sequence Flaws							Backward Sequence Flaws							Bidirectional Sequence Flaws							
	F_{last}^{add}	F_{ref}^{add}	F_{cost}^{add}	F_{CG}^{add}	F_{CGr}^{add}	F_{it}^{add}	F_{it}^{add}	B^{add}	B_{last}^{add}	B_{ref}^{add}	B_{cost}^{add}	B_{CG}^{add}	B_{CGr}^{add}	B_{it}^{add}	D^{add}	D_{last}^{add}	D_{ref}^{add}	D_{cost}^{add}	D_{CG}^{add}	D_{CGr}^{add}	D_{it}^{add}	D_{clo}^{add}
Abs. time (h)	4.5	4.7	6.5	6.0	5.7	5.5	7.5	6.3	6.4	8.3	7.7	7.5	7.0	6.9	8.6	7.1	10.1	9.5	9.1	8.6	8.2	7.5
Cost (k)	34.6	33.1	34.8	33.5	32.0	31.7	33.7	34.0	33.2	33.8	33.6	32.2	31.5	34.0	31.6	33.2	33.9	33.1	31.8	31.6	33.4	33.7
Ref. (M)	8.9	8.0	8.7	9.6	10.6	7.9	9.8	9.6	8.3	8.9	8.7	9.7	6.8	9.1	8.1	8.2	9.0	9.3	10.8	8.1	9.9	9.8
F. Flaw (M)	7.9	32.3	40.4	35.7	28.3	28.0	37.8	—	—	—	—	—	—	—	34.9	34.0	41.6	43.0	31.3	34.9	10.7	37.8
B. Flaw (M)	—	—	—	—	—	—	—	8.7	29.6	30.9	31.2	24.9	23.3	8.2	27.8	29.3	31.0	33.4	25.7	27.8	9.0	17.4
F. Flaw (%)	1.6	5.2	4.3	6.2	7.5	7.3	5.8	—	—	—	—	—	—	8.5	5.7	5.6	5.7	7.9	8.5	3.2	5.8	
B. Flaw (%)	—	—	—	—	—	—	—	2.5	5.1	4.6	4.4	6.2	6.0	2.3	7.8	5.1	4.6	4.8	7.0	7.8	2.6	3.7
F. Pos (%)	13.3	17.4	13.6	11.3	13.8	11.6	18.2	—	—	—	—	—	—	—	10.4	9.1	6.5	6.8	11.7	10.4	17.9	18.2
B. Pos (%)	—	—	—	—	—	—	—	4.2	3.3	3.8	3.7	5.1	3.4	4.1	3.4	3.2	3.8	3.4	5.3	3.4	3.6	3.6

Table 3: Coverage of additive abstractions. A bold value means the maximum value and * variant is the best strategy at each direction.

Domain	Forward Sequence Flaws							Backward Sequence Flaws							Bidirectional Sequence Flaws										
	F_*^{add}	F^{add}	F_{last}^{add}	F_{ref}^{add}	F_{cost}^{add}	F_{CG}^{add}	F_{CGr}^{add}	F_{it}^{add}	B_*^{add}	B^{add}	B_{last}^{add}	B_{ref}^{add}	B_{cost}^{add}	B_{CG}^{add}	B_{CGr}^{add}	B_{it}^{add}	D_*^{add}	D^{add}	D_{last}^{add}	D_{ref}^{add}	D_{cost}^{add}	D_{CG}^{add}	D_{CGr}^{add}	D_{it}^{add}	D_{clo}^{add}
agricola	5	5	5	5	5	5	5	5	5	5	5	5	5	5	5	5	5	5	5	5	5	5	5	5	5
airport	12	11	8	12	12	7	11	9	11	11	11	11	11	11	7	11	11	11	11	11	5	11	11	11	11
barman	12	12	11	11	12	12	10	12	12	12	12	12	12	12	12	12	12	12	12	12	12	12	11	12	12
blocksw	13	13	13	13	13	13	13	13	13	13	13	13	13	13	13	13	13	13	13	13	13	13	13	13	13
childsnack	5	5	5	5	5	5	5	5	5	5	5	5	5	5	5	5	5	5	5	5	5	5	5	5	5
data-net	16	13	13	13	13	14	13	16	15	15	13	15	15	14	13	15	15	15	13	15	15	14	12	15	15
depots	13	13	13	13	13	12	12	12	13	12	12	12	13	12	12	12	13	12	12	12	13	12	13	12	12
driverlog	7	7	7	7	7	6	7	7	8	7	7	7	7	6	8	7	8	7	7	8	8	6	8	7	7
elevators	14	11	14	11	11	12	11	14	14	14	11	14	14	11	11	14	14	14	11	14	14	11	11	14	14
floortile	6	6	6	6	6	6	6	5	6	6	6	6	6	6	6	6	6	5	5	5	6	6	5	6	6
freecell	14	13	13	13	14	12	13	13	14	13	13	13	12	12	14	13	14	13	13	13	12	13	13	14	14
ged	22	22	20	22	18	18	16	22	22	22	22	22	20	20	18	22	22	22	22	22	20	20	16	22	22
grid	15	14	14	15	15	15	15	14	16	14	14	14	14	14	16	14	15	14	14	14	15	15	15	14	14
grripper	12	12	12	12	12	12	12	12	12	12	12	12	12	12	12	12	12	12	12	12	12	12	12	12	12
hiking	11	9	10	10	10	10	9	11	10	10	9	10	10	10	9	10	11	10	9	10	11	10	9	10	10
logistics	21	21	21	21	21	19	21	21	21	21	21	21	21	20	21	21	21	21	21	21	21	19	21	21	21
miconic	5	5	5	5	5	5	5	5	5	5	5	5	5	5	5	5	5	5	5	5	5	5	5	5	5
mprime	13	10	13	10	12	6	6	13	14	11	9	14	12	6	7	11	14	14	9	14	14	6	7	12	12
nomystery	8	8	7	8	8	8	8	7	8	8	8	8	8	8	8	8	8	8	8	8	8	8	8	8	8
openstacks	6	6	6	6	6	6	6	6	6	6	6	6	6	6	6	6	6	6	6	6	6	6	6	6	6
organic-s	11	11	11	11	11	11	11	11	11	11	11	11	11	11	11	11	11	11	11	11	11	11	11	11	11
parcprinter	18	17	16	17	17	17	18	16	17	17	17	17	17	17	17	17	18	17	17	17	17	17	18	17	17
parking	10	8	8	8	9	9	10	8	9	8	8	8	8	9	8	8	10	8	8	8	8	9	10	8	8
pathways	14	14	14	14	11	13	10	14	14	14	14	14	14	11	11	14	14	14	14	14	14	13	10	14	14
pegsol	29	28	28	28	28	28	29	28	29	28	28	28	28	28	29	28	29	28	28	28	28	28	29	28	28
pipesw-not	21	21	21	21	19	20	20	21	20	20	19	20	20	20	20	20	20	20	19	20	19	20	20	20	20
pipesw-tank	15	15	15	15	15	15	15	15	15	15	15	15	15	15	15	15	15	15	15	15	15	15	15	15	15
rovers	4	4	4	4	4	4	4	4	4	4	4	4	4	4	4	4	4	4	4	4	4	4	4	4	4
satellite	9	9	9	9	9	9	9	9	9	9	9	9	9	9	9	9	9	9	9	9	9	9	9	9	9
scanalyzer	9	9	9	9	9	9	9	9	9	9	9	9	9	9	9	9	9	9	9	9	9	9	9	9	9
snake	15	15	15	15	15	15	15	15	15	15	15	15	15	15	15	15	15	15	15	15	15	15	15	15	15
sokoban	15	12	15	13	13	12	12	12	14	13	14	14	13	13	13	13	14	14	14	14	13	13	11	14	14
storage	14	14	14	14	14	6	14	14	14	14	14	14	14	7	14	14	14	14	14	14	14	7	14	14	14
termes	13	13	13	13	13	13	13	13	13	13	13	13	13	13	13	13	13	13	13	13	13	13	13	13	13
tetris	17	17	17	17	17	17	17	17	17	17	17	17	17	17	17	17	17	17	17	17	17	17	17	17	17
thoughtful	5	5	5	5	5	5	5	5	5	5	5	5	5	5	5	5	5	5	5	5	5	5	5	5	5
tidybot	11	11	11	11	11	11	11	11	11	11	11	11	11	11	11	11	11	11	11	11	11	11	11	11	11
tp	3	3	3	3	3	3	3	3	3	3	3	3	3	3	3	3	3	3	3	3	3	3	3	3	3
transport	15	12	15	13	13	13	11	15	15	15	12	15	15	13	12	15	15	15	12	15	15	12	11	15	15
visitall	5	5	5	5	5	5	5	5	5	5	5	5	5	5	5	5	5	5	5	5	5	5	5	5	5
woodwork	5	5	5	5	5	5	5	5	5	5	5	5	5	5	5	5	5	5	5	5	5	5	5	5	5
zenotravel	19	15	18	15	14	13	16	19	16	16	15	15	15	14	16	16	16	16	15	16	15	14	15	16	16
Total	507	479	487	483	478	456	466	491	500	489	477	492	487	458	474	489	502	492	476	493	491	458	466	492	492